

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) - Serological surveillance in domestic ruminants in high-risk regions

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Serological surveillance in domestic ruminants in high-risk regions. (1; 2)
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of prevalence increase; Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution; Early detection of an increase in incidence i.e., early epidemic detection; Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen.
3	Target species and group	Domestic ruminants (cattle, goats and sheep).
4	Target sector / production type	Dairy animals.
5	Geographical area covered	In previous known affected areas, based on the prevalence on the territories of each Member State.
6	Age group	Adult animals which may have already developed a good immunity.
7	Sampling point and strategy	At the farm. Targeted to specific regions, within regions a representative sample. Each MS will have to decide its own representative sample on the basis of the animal population present in a given territory and the known prevalence of the disease in the given country
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited. May to November is the period with the highest prevalence of the disease in humans in the EU.
9	Sampling matrix	Whole blood.
10	Type of disease indicators	Antibodies.
11	Sampling unit	Herd (two stage sampling, herds and then animals).
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Goats and sheep.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Serological test: IgM- or IgG-capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) paired acute and convalescent sera for detecting seroconversion or rising titres; positive ELISA assays should be confirmed with serum neutralisation (SN) assays; cross-reactivity with other flaviviruses can occur. Plaque reduction/serum neutralisation test (PRSN) is considered the “gold standard” for detection. (3)
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Only applicable if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample (see 16)
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined and reported. Ideally 95 %.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	This activity targets a known population and the sensitivity of detection can be calculated if the sampling protocol ensures a representative sample, which can be achieved by different sampling strategies, including for instance random, stratified, or risk-based. Estimation of the sensitivity in the latter case depends on proper definition of the risk strata and their relative risks. The component is expected to have a high sensitivity.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever (CCHF), Lyme Borreliosis (LB), Anaplasma phagocytophilum, Rickettsia spp., Neoehrlichia mikurensis and zoonotic Babesia spp. (5)
18	References	<p>1) Casati Pagani S, Frigerio Malossa S, Klaus C, Hoffmann D, Beretta O, Bomio-Pacciorini N, Lazzaro M, Merlani G, Ackermann R, Beuret C. First detection of TBE virus in ticks and sero-reactivity in goats in a non-endemic region in the southern part of Switzerland (Canton of Ticino). Ticks Tick Borne Dis. 2019 Jun;10(4):868-874. doi: 10.1016/j.ttbdis.2019.04.006. Epub 2019 Apr 18. PMID: 31047827.</p> <p>2) Bauer BU, Könenkamp L, Stöter M, Wolf A, Ganter M, Steffen I, Runge M. Increasing awareness for tick-borne encephalitis virus using small ruminants as suitable sentinels: Preliminary observations. One Health. 2021 Feb 20;12:100227. doi: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100227. PMID: 33732862; PMCID: PMC7937955.</p>

		<p>3) WOAHA Disease card - Flavivirus (causing tick borne encephalitis) (Infection with), 2020</p> <p>4) Cisak E, Wójcik-Fatla A, Zając V, Sroka J, Buczek A, Dutkiewicz J. Prevalence of tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV) in samples of raw milk taken randomly from cows, goats and sheep in eastern Poland. Ann Agric Environ Med. 2010;17(2):283-6. PMID: 21186771.</p> <p>5) Springer A, Glass A, Topp A-K and Strube C (2020) Zoonotic Tick-Borne Pathogens in Temperate and Cold Regions of Europe—A Review on the Prevalence in Domestic Animals. Front. Vet. Sci. 7:604910. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2020.604910</p>
19	Additional comments	Prevalence information available: sheep (22.2%), goats (20.7%). (4)